

The Prison Chronicle

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Entry tags: Christianity, Christian, Latin Text, Religious Group, Catholic, Martyrs, Text, Hagiography, Chronicle, Medieval Christianity, Catholic text

During the high middle ages, conflicts between the worldly magnates such as kings/princes/emperors and between the power holders of the church such as archbishops/popes/bishops were a quite common feature seen quite often across Europe. One such situation is seen in Denmark in the late 1200s with a severe conflict breaking out between king Erik Menved of Denmark and archbishop Jens Grand of Lund. One, both highly important and probably also somewhat internationally unusual, source to this conflict is a chronicle probably written sometime after 23. December 1297, but before 23. February 1302. It is commonly called the prison chronicle and it documents the events around the archbishop's longstanding imprisonment. It seems to have been written by an anonymous cathedral canon from Lund archbishopric and seems to have been based partially on eye witness accounts and partially on the contemporary archives of Lund archbishopric. Although the chronicle should not be mistaken for a hagiographic text, as Jens Grand was also still alive when it was written, its author clearly imitates the genre of hagiography and portrays Jens Grand almost as a martyr saint in the chronicle. However, due to the strange circumstances of transmission, the original latin version of the chronicle is long lost, though, and the chronicle is now preserved only in a Danish translation edition produced by early Danish historian Arild Huitfeldt (1546-1609). Unfortunately, this also means that the chronicle has been completely unavailable as source materiale, up until now, for all foreign historians and researchers internationally not able to read Danish. For this very reason, instead of writing a prolonged introduction text to this entry, I have made it a priority instead to let the chronicle speak for itself by retelling its main content thus for the very first ever making the chronicle somewhat available to an international audience. Resumé or retelling of the main content of The Prison Chronicle: [It starts out with a short introduction left out here as its originality has been disputed]. [chapter 1]: In the year 1294, on the friday before Palm Sunday, in the morning between 5 and 6 AM, after Mass, Duke Christoffer was sent to archbishop Jens Grand of Lund in order to spy on him. He was sent by King Erik Menved of Denmark who was present in the town of Lund at the time. Duke Christoffer now talks to the archbishop telling him that king Erik is hostile towards him and offers to try to reconcile them. Archbishop Jens Grand claims to be unaware of having offended the king and accepts his offer. Before Christoffer leaves the archbishop then gives him 3 valuable gifts. Christoffer then leaves to consult with the king and afterwards arrives at the episcopal seat once again. Christoffer leads Jens Grand to believe that the king is with him this time, bus as soon as the archbishop goes outside to meet him, Duke Christoffer takes him prisoner on behalf of the king. Christoffer then walks into the choir of Lund cathedral where he takes also dean Jacob prisoner in the midst of church service still wearing his ecclesistical garments. Having done that Christoffer and his men then raids the houses of Jacob and Jens Grand stealing all their valuables. Jens Grand and dean Jacob are then led to the place where the king is staying and from there they are taken on the road and away from Lund while being humiliated in different ways along the way. [chapter 2]: Archbisop Jens Grand and dean Jacob arrives in the town of Helsingborg from where they are both thrown onto the Elsinore-Helsingborg ferry. While still being humiliated along the way, they are both being ferried to Zealand. Here, on that very same night, they are both jailed and chained in the royal castle of Søborg in Northern Zealand. The archbishop is jailed in the deepest dungeon below the tower and dean Jacob is put in another prison. The next morning dean Jacob is taken away to the royal castle of Kalundborg elsewhere on Zealand where he is now also jailed and chained in the deepest dungeon below the tower. The rest of the chapter describes how unfair it is that they were jailed and how extremely harsh the archbishop's conditions were while he was jailed. The archbishop becomes gravely ill because of this, but is denied a doctor and is also denied access to his religious books as well as to reading light. Having been stashed away

like this for 36 weeks, he is moved to another prison farther up in the tower, but he still remains chained. [chapter 3]: King Erik Menved arrives at Søborg castle to celebrate christmas there. On the second day after christmas archbishop Jens Grand is asked by an envoy from amongst the king's men whether he would like to reconcile with the king. Jens Grand then answered by asking why he should reconcile with him when he had never knowingly had any quarrels with him in the first place - asking: should I reconcile with him because he has imprisoned me when I was innocent? Jens Grand is then told that the king holds grudges against you because your kin participated in the murder of his father king Erik Klipping. Jens Grand then answered that I have already proven before him and before the council of the realm that I did not approve of that and that I did not even now about it until after it had already happened. The king then gave me a document as proof of his friendship and the queen dowager and the council helped me become archbishop. Ever since that I have served him faithfully. All of this I trust onto God. On the fourth day after this, two Danish bishops, who were allied with the king, arrived together with some members of the council of the realm. They all requested urgently that Jens Grand should reconcile with the king. Jens Grand then answered by repeating that he never knowingly had any quarrels with the king in the first place and that he is willing to stand trial. The king's men then hands Jens Grand a document and threatens to keep him imprisoned for the rest of his life unless he seals this document. The content of the document is then referenced in detail containing 8 specified points all of which the archbishop would have to promise to keep before his release from prison. They read the document to him, but Jens Grand answered that he would rather see king Erik cut off all limbs from his body before would give his consent to any of that. They then go back to the king with this answer and the king is enraged even saying to some that he would never let Jens Grand out of prison even if he was excommunicated a hundred times by the pope. It is told that Duke Christoffer would like to escape excommunication, but that the king wouldn't let him. [chapter 4]: The chapter starts out by listing the names of all 18 knights and men who were together with Duke Christoffer when he imprisoned the archbishop. Afterwards it tells about how duke Christoffer travelled back to Lund after he had imprisoned Jens Grand at Søborg castle. In Lund he entered the cathedral and broke into the sacristy where he broke up the chest which held all the documents and privileges of the church. He then tore off the seals from a large number of them and lit a fire in the choir before the altar where he burned them. All the gold and money and treasures and valuables of the cathedral which were kept in the sacristy duke Christoffer then took. He then gathered all the cathedral canons in the choir where he threatened them all on their life and estates unless they broke the interdict at once. In the name of the king, he also banned them from writing to the pope or to anyone else for help and support. Because of this no one in Denmark dared writing to the pope in Rome. [chapter 5]: A cathedral canon from Lund called Hans Sibrandtsøn, who were studying in France at the time, got word that archbishop Jens Grand had been imprisoned and then travelled to the pope to complain that the King of Denmark had imprisoned the archbishop. Pope Celestine V then wrote king Erik Menved ordering him to release Jens Grand and dean Jacob from prison and return their estates and money to them, but Erik Menved had the papal messenger murdered as soon as he had delivered the letter so that no one would know what had become of him. Dean Jacob managed to escape from the tower of Kalundborg castle after having been imprisoned there for 27 weeks and travelled to Ribe in Denmark planning on going to Rome. Erik Menved got word that he was in Ribe and tried to have him apprehended there, but Jacob fled the country and met with Pope Boniface VIII. This pope then sent papal legates to Denmark ordering Erik Menved to release Jens Grand and gave them authority to make king Erik stand trial. The pope also wrote all Danish bishops ordering them to help the papal legates and he authorized his legates to excommunicate Denmark and declare interdict if the king refused to release the archbishop from prison. Pope Boniface VIII also wrote to the clerics from Lund at Hammershus castle on Bornholm allowing them to give church service even though Denmark had been excommunicated and encourage them to retain from giving in to royal threats and not hand over this, rightfully archeiscopal, castle at Hammerhus to the king or his bailiffs. But while the papal legate was still on his way from Rome to Denmark, Jens Grand escaped from his prison in the tower of Søborg castle the chronicle now says. [chapter 6]: The chapter tells in great detail the story of how an unnamed cook at Søborg castle helped Jens Grand escape. The cook was drinking with the gaolers and pretended that he had got very drunk. Pretending to be drunk he offered the imprisoned archbishop his help by sending a message to the pope in Rome or to anywhere

else, but the gaoler did not take it seriously as he thought that the cook had said it because of drunkenness. Jens Grand meanwhile kept quiet. On the very next day the cook drank with the gaolers once again. While some of the gaolers had left to go to sleep and others had shortly run errands, the cook repeated his offer to the archbishop. Having understood that he meant it seriously, the archbishop instructed the cook to go Hans Rodis, canon in Copenhagen, and make him send the archbishop pen, ink and a rope ladder. The cook then left and soon came back with the things he had been instructed to fetch and the archbishop then wrote to the clerics at Hammerhus castle instructing them to send a ship including supplies to the coast near Søbørg castle while pretending to be fishermen. The cook then left to deliver the letter and meanwhile Jens Grand worked on chains with a file. By the grace of God no one neither heard this nor inspected the chains while this work took place. The archbishop in this way managed to free himself from the chains, but was so weakened that he could hardly stand or walk. The cook then came back and told him that the ship had arrived. At that time, though, the king was at Søbørg castle personally and therefore they had to pretend to be fishing and only come back to the coast near Søbørg at night. By the grace of God no rumours of the strange fishermen reached the ears of the king, however, and God also made king Erik Menved leave Søbørg castle entirely to go hunting near Tikøb taking all of his men with him leaving behind only one single gaoler and a few men including his sister's two sons. After the king had left, the remaining men began a drinking party and the cook drank with the gaoler and got him so drunk that he left to go to sleep. As soon as they had all gone to sleep, the cook tied the rope ladder to the iron in the window and helped the archbishop down the ladder, the cook going first and the archbishop after him. Having almost reached the ground, the archbishop had no more strength left in him, but the cook managed to ward off his fall. While the archbishop recovered, the cook removed the rope ladder in the way he had planned. The cook then led and carried Jens Grand to an arrow slit and from there they both climbed down the outer wall via the rope ladder with the cook climbing first. The lake and the moat were both frozen and the ice solid, thus after removing the rope ladder, the cook led Jens Grand across the frozen moat to the staples. The archbishop now had no more strength left and therefore asked the cook to go into the staples and take two horses. They rode from there down to the beach where they arrived an hour before sunrise. The cook then let the two horses run free and entered the ship together with the archbishop. Then follows a description of their sail through Øresund to Bornholm during which they have to stop first at the island of Hven and then, for one day and two nights, at the island of Saltholm near Copenhagen because of fog and bad weather. Arriving at Hammerhus castle on Bornholm, the archbishop's men at the castle are shocked to see Jens Grand so weakened and they even become fearful that he might die soon. When king Erik Menved got word of the news that Jens Grand had escaped, he sent out messages to all ferries on the island of Zealand and occupied them. He also searched for him day and night across woodlands, bogs and thickets, and he punished the gaolers severely, but all was in vain. [chapter 7]: At shrovetide the following year, the papal legate arrived in Denmark and handed the king the letter from the pope ordering the king to stand trial in Rome together with archbishop Jens Grand. The king answered that he obeyed the pope in these matters and in all other matters as a christian man should do. The legate also wrote to the archbishop who was still at Hammershus castle and also sent him a document from the king granting him safe-passage, and the legate therefore ordered the archbishop to come to Copenhagen. The archbishop, however, was still so weakened from the imprisonment that he was forced to decline as he could not travel. Having regained his health just after Easter, the archbishop now travelled to Copenhagen and met the legate there. Having conferred with the legate, the archbishop travelled on to Lübeck, where he waited for the legate to arrive. But the legate had been held up in Ribe, where he was together with the king. Jens Grand wrote the legate from Lübeck asking him what to do, and the legate replied that the king had refused to reconcile with the archbishop in Denmark, but that he was now preparing to go to Rome to settle affairs there. Receiving this reply, the archbishop thus travelled to Brügge and further on from there to Paris, as he dared not travel via the shortest route to Rome out of fear that the king's men might intervene there. He had to travel by carts or wagons as he could not ride being still too weakened from the imprisonment. [chapter 8]: In 1296, Jens Grand arrived to meet with the pope in Anagni and told him about his harsh imprisonment and complained that he would be suffering lifelong from this imprisonment in terms of health. The pope comforted him saying to his cardinals and other bishops and clerics, who were there, that many holy men in heaven had not suffered half as much for God's sake as he now had. The pope

asked Jens Grand to accompany him to Rome. Having been there awhile, king Erik Menved's chancellor arrived. This man was Martin of Dacia, Danish scholar of theology from Paris, who would act as procurator for the king during the trial. Then follows a description of the trial. The archbishop complains about being imprisoned for no good reason and being permanently weakened by it, he also complained that all of his earthly belongings as well as the belongings of dean Jacob had been robbed, furthermore he complained that duke Christoffer had broken into the sacristy and taken the documents and treasures of Lund cathedral, he also complained about further thefts of income of Lund archbishopric done by Erik Menved, furthermore he complained that Erik Menved had imprisoned a cleric from Lund while he travelled with a letter from Jens Grand to the archbishop in Sweden, and furthermore he complained that king Erik Menved had broken into the sacristy of Lund cathedral personally and taken many of the letters and privileges belonging to the church, he also complained that the king had beaten up a cathedral canon called Christian and ripped his coat to pieces when Christian had tried to prevent him from taking the documents in the sacristy, furthermore he complained that the king had withheld all cathedral canons all night forcing them to write and seal all letters and documents that Erik Menved wanted them to write while his men were sitting all night in the house of the canons and in the choir of the cathedral emptying several barrels of beer acting as if they had entered an inn. Jens Grand also complained that in the morning the king had threatened to put all canons in irons unless they broke the interdict and celebrated Mass even though the realm had been excommunicated by a papal messenger whom Erik Menved had even had murdered in secrecy so that no one knew what had become of him. Furthermore, Jens Grand also complained that the king had taken all the belongings of Hans Rodis, canon of Copenhagen, because he had helped Jens Grand escape from prison. Finally he also complained that Erik Menved had confiscated valuables from a canon in Lund called Peder because he had travelled to the archbishop in Rome, and the king had also taken money from another official as well as confiscated the tithes of Lund archbishopric and apprehended another canon in Lund called Henrik Blomme and taken all of his belongings too. Amongst many more such complaints these complaints were all presented during the trial. The king's chancellor excused the king as much as he could, but it was all in vain as the papal legates themselves could testify to its truthfulness. The papal verdict then ordered the king to pay compensation to the archbishop. [Now follows a short ending left out here as its originality has been disputed].

Date Range: 1297 CE - 1302 CE

Region: Parts of Denmark where The Prison Chronicle takes place primarily.

Region tags: Denmark

The content of The Prison Chronicle takes place primarily in Zealand, Scania, and Bornholm. Outside Denmark, though, parts of the ending takes place in Italy.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Benedicte Fønnesbech-Wulff, Bo Fritzboøger, Kurt Villads Jensen, Michael Kræmmer, Martin Palsgaard: *Hellere Fanden Selv End Erik på Tronen. Konflikten mellem Jens Grand og Erik Menved 1294-1302*. Odense University Studies in History and Social Sciences vol. 214, Odense Universitetsforlag, Odense 1999 (most recent reprinting of the chronicle as translated by Arild Huitfeldt into Renaissance era Danish).

– Source 2: Richard Mott: Fængselskrøniken. Arild Huitfeldts gengivelse af en fortælling fra middelalderen, omsat til nutidsdansk og med noter, Forlaget Tellus, 2003 (most recent printed version of the chronicle adapted into modern day Danish).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.crassus.dk/Faengselskroeniken/fkroenike_1.html

– Source 1 Description: Adaptation of the text into modern day Danish (only edition of Mott's book from 2003).

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: https://www.crassus.dk/Faengselskroeniken/fkroenike_1.html

Notes: adaptation of the text into modern day Danish.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: none of these mentioned

Notes: It was most likely written on parchment, although nowadays the chronicle is only preserved in Arild Huitfeldt's printed book edition.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The manuscript of the chronicle was probably kept in the library/archive of Lund archbishopric until c. the end of the middle ages, later on being handed over to Arild Huitfeldt by some anonymous friend - until finally disappearing entirely after Huitfeldt already published his translation edition.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The author was not necessarily paid for writing the chronicle, but he must have been a canon of the holy chapter in Lund and his livelihood and income thus must have been dependent on his status as a cathedral canon.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that this is personified in Jens Grand via his position as archbishop of Lund.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that such clergymen also sometimes were or could be political officials to some extent.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: This is clearly visible in the chronicle as e.g. in places where it is described how some of the other Danish bishops also serve king Erik Menved as political officials.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: It seems to have been written by an anonymous canon of Lund archbishopric.

↳ Present part-time?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: male

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: Danish

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

Notes: This was hardly a written rule, but most canons of Lund probably stemmed from the upper classes of Danish society.

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, but in reality a lot of them probably were.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: It was written in latin, but is preserved now in Danish only.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Although the names of the canons of Lund changed from time to time, of cause.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The original manuscript is not preserved.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: Although in a certain way, yes, as the chronicle clearly condemns the behaviour of king Erik menved and duke Christoffer and generally sides with the church and clergymen of Lund.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: chronicle

–Other [specify]: chronicle

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none of the above.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that the chronicle references the content of a large number of legal documents.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none of the above.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that, according to the chronicle, it is God himself who performs miracles in order to help Jens Grand escape from prison.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that God helps Jens Grand escape.

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that God helps Jens Grand escape.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: Although perhaps yes in so far as the chronicle condemns the moral and behaviour of king Erik Menved.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: The chronicle clearly sides with the archbishop portraying him as righteous while the king and his men are all portrayed as unjust.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: The chronicle condemns the fact that king Erik imprisons Jens Grand and dean Jacob so unjustly as they were both men with university education and this was used against them.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Although the life of a cleric in Lund did, of course.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Although it is described how Jens Grand is denied proper food and beer during his harsh imprisonment.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Although the life of a cleric in Lund did, of course. In a way Jens Grand's imprisonment is also portrayed as a sacrifice of time in order to suffer for God's sake.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: Although his escape from prison and the climb down the wall is portrayed as quite risky.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: No, but the text describes the desecration of a sacred space as when duke Christoffer is burning documents in the choir as well as when it is mentioned that king Erik Menved's men were having a drinking party in the choir.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: An archbishopric and the cathedral chapter

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The archbishopric and the cathedral chapter in whose library/archive the manuscript of the text seems to have remained.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None of the above. When and why the medieval manuscript of the chronicle disappeared is unknown except for the fact that it could not have happened until after 1599 at the earliest, as this is the year in which Arild Huitfeldt published his translation edition and thus must have used the manuscript.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is mentioned that both Jens Grand and dean Jacob had studied in Valland and France, and that Martin of Dacia had studied in Paris. It is also mentioned that Hans Sibrandsøn was studying in Orleans when he became involved.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– No

Notes: Lund archbishopric did, of course, but it is not mentioned in the text. Tithes are mentioned, however, as part of the income that king Erik had unjustly confiscated from the archbishopric.

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Notes: But there are many descriptions of the king and the duke unjustly confiscating income and valuables from the clergymen of Lund archbishopric.

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: But it describes how archbishop Jens Grand is denied proper food and beer during his imprisonment while specifying how bad the food really is - saying that they hoped that he would soon die from starvation.

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